

Marketing tests and guidelines for designing marketing strategies

D5.19

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Short Description	
<p>This deliverable describes the activities conducted under Task T5.8 that aimed to develop marketing strategies for locally produced packaged foods in Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda by examining consumer responses using biometric tools such as eye-tracking and emotional recording. Two studies were conducted: sensory evaluation (Study A) and packaging design assessment (Study B), with willingness to pay (WTP) as the dependent variable. Findings revealed that packaging design significantly influenced WTP, with attributes like product visibility and ingredient-focused illustrations driving higher consumer acceptance. Conversely, sensory variables like taste and texture were secondary predictors. Emotional responses showed limited impact on WTP. Overall, packaging emerged as the key determinant of consumer valuation.</p>	
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Introduction

Increase in economy and prosperity among consumers follow changes in diet and challenge health among the population, which is the case for many African countries (Kengne et al., 2013). The continent has experienced increase in prosperity and wealth and with malnutrition as the unfortunate side effect of this development, which is a reason for looking at food innovation in an African context (Reardon et al. 2021). Research on consumers' evaluation of food quality and their willingness to pay (WTP) for processed and packed food in African countries is limited (Mihafu, Issa and Kamiyango, 2020).

The African food market is a mix of traditional small shops, kiosks, and large-size supermarkets but all with an increased share of processed and packaged food (Khonje et al., 2020). Re-thinking food supply enrolls stakeholders from farmers, industry, and not least ends consumers who will be those to pay for the new food product. It requires careful consideration about challenging consumers' habitual behavior (van't Riet et al., 2011).

The price a consumer is willing to pay for a food product is highly related to the subjective perceived quality of the food. From the producers' viewpoint price is more objectively related to expenses for producing the food product such as raw material expenses, production costs, logistics, and marketing, which do not necessarily reflect the subjective experienced quality. Innovative thinking and changes in a food system entails in a nutshell this uncertainty about the gap between consumer's perceived quality and how to set the price for the new food product (Priilaid and Hall, 2016).

The aim for this task 5.8 is to test consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) for new healthy, packed, and locally produced food in Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda. Behavioral responses through scale evaluations in combination with bio-metric data from eye-tracking and facial expressions provides guidelines for designing marketing strategies for innovative food products in East Africa.

Guidelines for marketing planning

The purpose of task T5.8 is to provide guidelines for testing and designing marketing strategies in Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda. The task is to investigate consumers' response to local produced and packed food using bio-metric techniques—eye-tracking and face recordings. The focus is on consumer's response to new packed foods launched on the market, and types of packaging design with specific labels printed on the front. The data collection utilized bio-metric testing as shown in the illustration 1 below.

Illustration 1 – screen-based eye-tracking and emotional recording using lab-top computers

The following guiding research questions were:

RQ1: Will information given on packaging increase test persons' willingness to pay (WTP)?

RQ 2: Will specific attributes such as localness/healthiness/ingredients increase WTP?

RQ 3: Will taste be stronger predictor for WTP than packaging design?

RQ 4: Will emotional responses influence WTP?

Setup and data collection were made from medio 2023 to medio 2024.

The general research design

The overall research design was the same for Tanzania, Kenya, and Uganda and consisted of two parts—study A focused on sensory evaluation/taste, and study B focused on visual perception of packaging. Both studies use WTP as the dependent variable, enabling cross-product comparisons by controlling for differences in national currency and product categories. The study targets urban consumers and their evaluation of packaged food products, differentiating from rural market food products, which are typically unpackaged and sold on markets and along roadsides.

The taste test was conducted before packaging evaluation in order to avoid bias from the packaging design on the taste. Both study A and study B were carried out by using a lab-top computer utilizing the iMotions software version 9 and the AFFECTIVA algorithm. The facial expression was recorded through a Logitech HD Pro webcam, and a Tobii Nano Pro eye-tracker recorded eye movements.

Study A–taste

Test persons are exposed to novel food products made by the enrolled Universities. Each product is evaluated on Likert scales related to six sensory variables—aroma, appearance, color, taste, texture, and general acceptance. During the tasting the test persons’ facial expression were recorded and used as an independent variable for emotional engagement. There was no time limit, and the test persons were asked to take the time needed for the sensory evaluation.

Study B–packaging

Immediately after the tasting, the test person was exposed to different variations of packaging specifically related to the tasted product. The test person was further instructed to look at each packaging and indicate an attitude whether it stated *Local Product*, *Good Nutrition*, *Good Quality* or *Nice Taste*. After each packaging the test persons indicated WTP. During the exposure of each packaging the test persons’ eye movements were recorded together with the facial expression.

The design of the packaging variations utilized different visual elements such as text font, background color, claims, graphic symbols, illustration, and package types. These variations were made in a matrix model, so each feature could be isolated and analyzed individually. Each exposure of a packaging lasted 6 seconds, followed by the indication of attitudes to one of the four statements and the indication about WTP. For these indications there was no time limit. The different packaging designs were randomized to reduce sequential biasing of test persons.

Lastly the test persons gave data related to demographics.

Illustration 2 – study A–tasting the food product and study B–visual perception of packaging/statements

The specific research design

The studies took place at enrolled Universities in Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania and respondents were recruited from local lists aiming for 200 test persons at each location.

Tanzania – Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro (SUA)

A body of 200 respondents (166f, 44m) were tested on three different porridge products and with 16 different packaging designs. The packaging features included text font, different types of ingredient list, and different illustration of either people or ingredients (see Appendix). The data collection took place in October 2023 over a period of three weeks.

Uganda – Makerere University, Kampala (MAK)

A body of 200 respondents (97f, 106m) were tested on two food products—dried eggplant and daddies (a crouton shaped biscuit local to Uganda). Subsequently the test persons were exposed to eight packaging designs related to the two types of food products (8x2). The packaging features included text font, with or without a view to the food product through a “window” in the packaging, packaging color (brown vs. colorful), and statements related to either origin or nutrition (see Appendix). The data collection took place in February 2024 over a period of three weeks.

Kenya – Faculty of Agriculture, University of Nairobi (UoN)

A body of 200 respondents (138f, 61m, 1o) were tested on tamarillo juice and quinoa cookies, and subsequently exposed to eight packaging designs related to the two types of food products (8x2). The packaging features included imagery of people vs. ingredients, colorful vs. brown paper packaging, and origin vs local statements (see Appendix). The data collection took place in March and April 2024 over a period of four weeks.

Data analysis

The data from the three countries was merged into one dataset, which enabled analysis across countries, food types and packaging features. The different packaging features were marked as special areas of interest (AOIs) in order to analyze the ratio of visual attention each test person has dedicated to the specific packaging feature. Eye-tracking metrics e.g., dwell time on AOIs were converted into relative percentages of total view time, in order to standardize across stimuli and control for inter-individual variation in viewing behavior.

For the statements the data was categorical encoded as binary variables which enabled logistic regression and mediation analyses. The statement *Nice Taste* served as a control variable whereas *Local Product*, *Good Nutrition*, and *Good Quality* were analyzed as core variables to the study. These are then used to approximate consumer attitudes and to predict the respondent's WTP.

Linear mixed-effects models were used to model WTP, accounting for the nested structure of the data and random intercepts for respondents. This approach was consistent across both studies. Mediation Analysis was employed to investigate the indirect effects of predictor variables, e.g., sensory attributes, AOI metrics and emotions on WTP and through mediating variables, e.g., general acceptance, binary statement classification. Both parametric and bootstrapped mediation approaches were utilized to assess robustness.

Findings

WTP was found to be significant higher when people saw and interpret the packaging designs (study B) compared to the situation where people tasted the food products (study A). This is found for all three countries, and it aligns with findings from the FoodLAND study in Morocco and Tunisia where virgin olive oils were tested. WTP increases with visual perception, which was validated across all product categories tested in this study.

The condensed answer of the taste test can be interpreted as people are more certain of the pricing when seeing the product packaging. Yet, the packaging design does also leave room for uncertainty, which is based on a higher spread in WTP for packaging evaluation compared to taste evaluation.

Tasting the food product

For the tasting (study A) the *general acceptance* variable was found to be a meaningful predicted for the five other sensory variables—*taste*, *aroma*, *appearance*, *texture*, and *color*. Each sensory variable contribute significantly to WTP, both directly and through its influence on general acceptance. Yet, the mediation test shows that *general acceptance* functions as the best sensory variable for explaining WTP. The model also indicates that *taste* is the most critical driver of general acceptance, followed by *texture*, *appearance*, *aroma*, and *color*. This means that improving taste and texture could have the most pronounced impact on general acceptance.

Emotions generally play a very small role in predicting WTP. Generally, the effect sizes are negligible if at all significant. Some interaction effects can be found on the sensory variables, where neutral and positive emotions can significantly moderate the effect of *general acceptance*, albeit with very small.

Seeing the food packaging

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Statements had a large and significant impact on WTP. Using *Nice Taste* as the baseline, *Good Quality* and *Good Nutrition* explains best WTP, whereas if the product is categorized as *Local Product* the WTP decreases. The emotional states of respondents can explain WTP variance directly and at a significant level, but with very small impact. Some moderation effects between emotions and statements were significant, but overall emotions did not improve the model.

In terms of packaging types, placing an illustration of people on the packaging decreases WTP, which can be compared to showing illustrations of the ingredients which increased WTP. See the core product through a “window” in the packaging increased WTP and was observed to be correlated to attributing high quality to the food product.

Packaging with health claims, as opposed to claiming localness, significantly increased the likelihood of respondents attributing the products as *Good Nutrition*. There was found no significant effect of claiming *Good Quality* to WTP.

There was we found no impact on WTP from emotions, which could be a consequence of the research design in study B, where the stimuli is limited to 6 seconds of exposure. This might be too short to capture a relevant emotional response to the stimuli. Furthermore, lower face movements from tasting in study A impacts face muscles related to facial expression analysis making the impact of emotions unclear.

Conclusion

The objectives for T5.8 was to indicate a way to market new food products and find the best way to get potential consumers' accept. In this combined study, where taste and packaging design were in focus, the data outlined clearly that packaging contributes to explaining variance of the products with the highest effect sizes over the sensory evaluations of the food product. The conclusion is that the value is found in the packaging.

The importance of having the optimal packaging design for a new innovative food product is not to be understated, as the expectations and in this study measured by WTP for the product are formed by the product packaging. Having a window in the packaging to show the product both signifies quality but is also argued to further align visual expectations of the product. Interestingly packaging colored as brown to appear bio-friendly did not impact WTP.

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Appendix

Example of packaging tested in Tanzania

Example of packaging tested in Uganda

Example of packaging tested in Kenya

